

BARBARISM IN THE EYES OF LINGUISTS

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Inter-linguistic interactions are a natural phenomenon that occurs in the languages of each world and is characteristic of itself. During periods, certain words come into one language from other foreign languages under the influence of various factors. Such words are called barbarisms. Currently, there are several interpretations of the concept of "barbarism". Some linguists say the term is derived from the Greek word "barbarismos", while others say it comes from the Latin word "barbaris". In both cases, it means "foreign, alien". Thus, in the dictionary of foreign words (I.V. Lyoxin and F.N. Edited by the Petrov) barbarism in a broad sense: "given as a word or phrase derived from another language and borrowed from another language" [7, p. 120].

A. Reformatsky interprets the concept of barbarism as "foreign words denoting colorfulness in describing alien realities and customs that are self-centered" [4, p. 137–138]. In the 1960 N. Golovina gave barbarism such a definition: "barbarism is the use of foreign words or phrases into speech without necessity" [3, p. 19]. The scientist brings savagery closer to lexical tools that block speech and disrupt its purity: dialectisms, jargon, vulgarisms, suffixes, complement words and clericalisms [1, p. 18–19]. An important aspect noted by linguists (a. V. Bride, N. M. Shansky, I. B. Golub, V. N. Suzdaltseva) is that there are other words that replace the existing barbarian words in one language, thus, due to the use of barbarism, words that already exist in one language are repeated, such as coffee-coffee, fast food - fast food – fast food, cadre-worker, etc.

T. V. Novikova considers barbarism to be "any units of a foreign language that have entered functionally in a stylistic direction, adapted and in the same language, but have not yet entered the language system, do not have full rights, are not recorded in normative academic dictionaries", [Novikova, 2003, V. 58].

I. G. Dobrodomov mentions the following signs of barbarism:

- 1) Words whose origin is foreign, i.e. barbarisms, are appropriated words;
- 2) Words in which frequently used by young people who have entered the new URF and are "in harmony with the Times" [2, p. 158].

To understand what barbarism is, there received different definitions from different sources. Barbarisms are words in other languages used in conversation or writing, but not at all assimilated, even if there are equivalents in the language. Nevertheless, since these words to some extent "adapt" to language norms, their origin from a foreign language is very clearly felt.

Barbarism is a foreign word or phrase that is famous for being used in certain situations that have entered a language and are not mastered.

Barbarism is a foreign word or phrase that is not fully mastered by the language, perceived as foreign as a violation of the norm of the language.

Barbarisms are derived words used by the people of the United Kingdom, often not assimilated and assimilated, such as addio (Italian), tete - a tete (French), dolce vita (Italian), duende (Spanish), etc.

N. Golovina, barbarisms are words or phrases in a foreign language that are included in speech without any need [3, p.19]. The scientist brings barbarisms closer to lexical tools that

disrupt speech in its purity: dialectics, jargon, vulgarism, swear words, parasitic words and chancellorisms. [Pp. 1, 18-19].

D. E. Rosenthal and M. A. Telenkova's dictionary-reference barbarism signs include weak assimilation of words, and often due to grammatical difficulties, words or phrases in a foreign language are incompletely absorbed by another language in such a way that " [Page 5, 189] has been defined.

Thus, barbarisms are foreign derived words that exist in a language that retain a foreign form, i.e. foreign pronunciation and spelling.

Such words have synonyms in the general dictionary layer. Barbarisms are not inclined to develop meanings, they are monosemantic lexical units.

It should be noted that barbarisms were recorded and used in dictionaries, mainly in the fiction or journalistic style. They often play the role of stylistic devices by conveying the local atmosphere or by emphasizing that this is happening in another country.

To know the difference between barbarisms and simple words entering from real foreign languages, it is necessary to prohibit that barbarisms, unlike foreign words, will be included in the dictionary even if the meaning of the original word is around, while foreign words are not recorded in dictionaries at all, while barbarisms have found their place in full English dictionaries. Usually foreign words and barbarisms in works of art will be written in italics.

From the analysis of definitions, it can be seen that barbarisms (derivations) are given by:

1. They can be described as neologisms if they represent new concepts.
2. They can be described as egotisms if they represent cultural reality.
3. They can be described as jargon if they belong to a certain social or professional group.
4. Foreign jargon (suffixes in the language (foreign language in the form of embedded phrases).

Some linguists promote the non-use of barbarian terms because it can also convey negative connotations such as ignorance, uncivilization, and rudeness. In our study, the term "barbarianism" has no negative connotations; we use this term to distinguish between pronouns.

In connection with the emergence of new pronouns in the language, in some cases, we consider it justified to highlight new layers of the dictionary and explain the definition of new names.

Words of the language derived from other languages present in the vocabulary can be classified as follows:

Source of acquisition from another language, assimilation by what side of the word is borrowed and by level. I want to dwell on the last aspect. To do this, first of all, it is necessary to understand what assimilation is. I. V. In Arnold's lexicology of the English language: "Assimilation of words from other languages-these words can be partial or complete according to the phonetic, graphic and morphological standards of the language and its semantic system. »

The degree of assimilation depends on the duration, frequency of the word and its use. Arnold proposes the following classification:

Words from other languages:

1. Fully assimilated
2. Partly from other languages

3. Not assimilated at all or barbarisms - will be in the state.

Fully assimilated barbarian words are found in all languages. Examples include barbarian words (cheese, wall, street) entered from Latin TII, barbarian words entered from Scandinavian TII (husband, root, gate; verbs: call, take, want, and adjectives: happy, ill, wrong). These barbarian words are subject to all morphological, phonetic rules of tilling, which they come into, and are actively involved in making a word form according to the spelling standards of the English language. They cannot be separated phonetically.

Arnold groups partially assimilated barbarian words into four:

a.) semantically unassigned barbarian words because they are things or phenomena specific to the country from which they are derived.

b.) ungrammatical barbarian words, such as nouns derived from Latin or Greek, as well as a proper form of plural.

c.) phonetically completely unassuming barbarian words, such as French words: machine, police.

d.) graphically incomplete barbarian words. Barbarian words, which are part of this group, are very numerous. Among them are French words, in which the finite consonant is not pronounced: ballet.

3.) Unlimited barbarian words.

The suction process can be very deep. The origin of such barbarian words is not noticed by English speakers and is determined only with the help of etymological analysis.

In linguistics, the most common understanding of the term "barbarism" is that it is built in contrast to the foreign elements it is assimilated. Among the concepts, the main thing that defines barbarianism is that the lexeme is not developed in the receptive language (L. P. Krysin, N. M. Shansky, M. I. Fomina, V. V. Kolesov, I. B. The opinion of Golub et al); as well as the lack of rigor in dictionaries (A. A. Bride, I. B. Golub, L. I. Rahmanova's opinion), the use of a foreign word both in a foreign language and in other language graphics (A. A. Reformatsky, L. P. Krysin, M. I. Fomina), low frequency and use only in a specific context (L. P. Krysin), use in separate groups of speakers (D. N. Shmelev); occasional use (L. P. Krysin, I. B. Golub) are the basic concepts that define barbarism.

The opinions of scientists about the future fate of barbarisms are divided, some of which say that due to occasional use, they may completely disappear, others say it is possible (D.N. Shmelev), or, conversely, prohibits the eventual recognition of a foreign language as an original lexical compound (N.M. Shansky, I.B. Golub).